

Eyelid Myokymia: A comprehensive Narrative Review

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Abstract

A disorder called myokymia is characterized by the involuntary fine rippling or quivering of the muscles. Eyelid myokymia is a condition that typically affects the muscles surrounding the eyes, though it can also affect other muscles. Myokymia is infrequently linked to more severe illnesses like multiple sclerosis (MS) or nerve damage. Cause : it is typically brought on by exhaustion, stress, alcohol and caffeine consumption, eye strain, dietary imbalances, etc. Symptoms: Myokymia is characterized by involuntary muscle twitches that resemble minute rhythmic contractions that are visible beneath the skin, as well as a tingling sensation that may feel like something is “crawling” or “rippling” in the affected area. Diagnosis : of this condition is primarily based on clinical evaluation and other conditions to rule out more serious conditions like hemifacial spasm or blepharospasm. Treatment: Firstly, make lifestyle modifications – Reduce stress , try yoga ,improve sleep,reduce alcohol and caffeine,eye care,diet and supplements. In circumstance when the injury is serious or ongoing,botox injection may be utilized to momentarily paralyze the afflicted muscle. Prognosis : Eyelid myokymia often cures on its own in a few weeks and is benign. Though they are uncommon, persistent cases could need additional testing to rule out underlying diseases. Effectively reducing the frequent and intensity of episode can be achieved by managing triggers such as stress, exhaustion ,and eyestrain.

Keywords:

Eyelid , Myokymia , Multiple sclerosis , Neurocysticercosis , Muscle.

Introduction

Resources appraising movement disorders in multiple sclerosis (MS) differ in clinical characteristics and accurate prevalence data[1,2,3]. A condition known as myokymia is characterized by involuntary, fine, undulating, non-synchronous striated muscle fiber contractions that cause the skin's surface to visibly ripple [4]. The most prevalent kind of focal facial myokymia affects the orbicularis oculi muscle, resulting in eyelid myokymia.[5]. Patients with eyelid myokymia usually report their condition as minor, bothersome twitches of either the upper or lower eyelid [6]. The primary inhibitory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system (CNS) is gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), and epilepsy is linked to the underregulation of this amino acid [7]. Since GABA cannot pass through the blood–brain barrier, Satzinger et al. set out to construct a lipophilic GABA analogue that could pass through the barrier through passive diffusion when they discovered gabapentin (GBP), 1-(aminomethyl) cyclohexane acetic acid, in 1976 [8] GBP did not bind to plasma proteins or undergo hepatocellular metabolism. Years later, Su et al. found that GBP was really transported to the central nervous system (CNS) through the system L-transporter in cultured astrocytes in a rat brain cortex, defying the original blood–brain barrier diffusion concept [9]. Neurocysticercosis (NCC) is a specific form of cysticercosis that affects the central nervous system (CNS). It is caused by the tapeworm *Taenia solium* (*T. solium*), which is often found in pigs. The association of cysticercosis and CNS infection was first extensively described in the early 20th century by English authors. This finding can be explained by the fact that many of the patients reported had a history of travel to work in India, Egypt, and Gibraltar, places known for a high incidence of cysticercosis. When these travelers returned to the UK, the British Army medics reported their possibly imported cases. In the 1930s, a large number of cases were reported by physicians of the Royal Army Medical Corps working at the Queen Alexandra Military Hospital at Millbank by the Thames River.[10] This cestode infection is classified by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a “neglected tropical disease,” which represents a diverse group of communicable diseases prevailing in tropical areas in about 150 countries, affecting >1 billion people. Common endemic areas include Asia, Eastern Europe, and South America. The WHO proposed in the early 2000s that effective control can be achieved when selected public health approaches are combined and applied locally.[11] Pigs are commonly the intermediate host for *T. solium*. Humans are the definitive host, but can serve as intermediate as well. NCC occurs due to the accidental ingestion of eggs of the pork tapeworm by humans, resulting in the development of the larval form of *T. solium* (cysticercus) in the brain.[12] It is worth mentioning that NCC is only acquired from the fecal-oral route (ingestion of eggs), not via the ingestion of cysticerci in undercooked pork, which is associated with taeniasis.[12] One particular type of cysticercosis that affects the central nervous system (CNS) is called neurocysticercosis (NCC). *Taenia solium*, often known as *T. solium*, is the tapeworm that causes it and is frequently found in pigs. Early in the 20th century, English writers provided the first comprehensive descriptions of the link between cysticercosis and CNS infection. This result can

be explained by the fact that a large number of the patients had previously traveled to work in countries with high rates of cysticercosis, such as Gibraltar, Egypt, and India. The British Army medics reported these passengers' potentially imported cases when they arrived back in the UK. Physicians from the Royal Army Medical Corps who worked at the Queen Alexandra Military Hospital recorded a lot of instances in the 1930s. Usually, pigs serve as *T. solium's* intermediate host. Although they are the ultimate host, humans can also act as an intermediary. The larval form of *T. solium* (cysticercus) develops in the brain as a result of humans inadvertently consuming pork tapeworm eggs, which causes NCC. It is important to note that consuming eggs through the fecal-oral route is the sole way to contract NCC. Taeniasis-causing cysticerci in undercooked pork is not a viable route of acquisition. Sulfamate-substituted medication topiramate (TPM) has several modes of action. It also suppresses carbonic anhydrase, increases potassium channels while inhibiting sodium channels, and activates postsynaptic gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors [13,14,15]. TPM has an elimination half-life of roughly 24 hours and is eliminated by the kidneys. In 1979, while doing research at Ortho-McNeil Pharmaceuticals, pharmacists Joe Gardocki and Bruce Maryanoff synthesized TPM for the first time. Its anticonvulsant properties were discovered when researchers tested it on mice. In 1996, the US FDA first authorized TPM as an antiepileptic medication for use as an adjuvant therapy alongside other drugs. It was authorized in 2004 to prevent adult migraine migraines. Additionally, in 2012, the FDA approved the use of the extended-release formulation in conjunction with phentermine for the control of adult weight [16,17]. TPM is presently used to treat adults and adolescents 12 years of age and older for partial-onset and generalized tonic-clonic seizures as well as migraine prophylaxis [18]. Bipolar disorder, borderline personality disorder, alcoholism, and binge eating disorder are among the conditions for which TPM is used off-label. With more than 10 million prescriptions filled, TPM was the 68th most prescribed drug in 2019 [19]. Like any drug, there is a list of side effects associated with TPM. There may also be paresthesias, dysgeusia, fatigue, drowsiness, dizziness, uncoordinated movements, diarrhea, and weight loss. There may also be mental health concerns such as disorientation, trouble focusing, memory problems, and speech/language difficulties [20]. The most well-known adverse effect on the eyes is called choroidal effusion syndrome (CEFS), which can cause a sharp shift in myopia and acute angle-closure glaucoma (AACG). Retinal complications, uveitis, visual field deficits, myokymia, neuro-ophthalmic complications, thicker corneas, and maybe scleritis are possible additional problems. Any sulfonamide medication carries a 3% risk of side effects [21]. The total number of TPM-induced ocular adverse effects is unknown. On the other hand, the rate of AACG, the most feared ocular complication, is anticipated to be roughly three per 100,000 [22].

Aetiology

There is still some confusion regarding the cause of myokymia.[23][24] Nonetheless, it mainly affects healthy individuals and is brought on by exhaustion, anxiety, stress, exercise, and coffee use [25][26]. Eyelid myokymia usually affects one of the lower eyelids' orbicularis oculi, while it can also occasionally affect the upper eyelids. These erratic contractions can last for weeks or months and are typically unilateral and sporadic. Myokymia of the eyelids is usually benign, self-limiting, and unrelated to any illnesses [27]. Potential initiating elements encompass tension, exhaustion, and overindulgence in caffeine or alcohol. On rare occasions, eyelid myokymia can develop

either as a precursor or as a component of face myokymia, which is a condition marked by persistent, uncontrollable facial muscle spasms linked to multiple sclerosis and brain stem tumors [27]. Eyelid myokymia can be brought on by drugs such as flunarizine, topiramate, clozapine, and gold salts. However, myokymia caused by medicine is not common.[28] Multiple sclerosis, autoimmune disorders, and brainstem pathologies including pontine gliomas are among the other reasons that have been documented.[26]

Pathophysiology

It is still unclear how eyelid myokymia pathophysiologically works. Electrophysiologically, one motor unit can discharge at a frequency of 3 to 8 Hz in rhythmic or semi-rhythmic spurts, however 60 Hz has been observed at times. These muscle discharges are not coordinated and occur at intervals of 100 to 200 milliseconds. Although voluntary movements may cause spontaneous discharges to increase, these actions do not cause them to begin.[29] Many of the cases of superior oblique myokymia are assumed to be caused by ephaptic impulse transmission.[30] As was previously mentioned, there is now substantial evidence linking the pathophysiology of MoS to antibodies against two VGKC complex proteins, CASPR2 and LGI1.[31] While LGI1 is present in both the central and peripheral nervous systems, CASPR2 is primarily expressed in the peripheral nervous system. Experimental data suggests that these antibodies block voltage-gated potassium outward currents, which are necessary for the repolarization of the motor nerve, hence causing neuronal hyperexcitability. Brain tissue immunostaining reveals that these antibodies target subtle differences in neuronal substrates, which are probably responsible for the unique clinical characteristics associated with Morvan syndrome.[32] A vast range of clinical manifestations are included in MoS. REM sleep behavioral abnormalities, limbic encephalitis, hyponatremia, and typical faciobrachial dystonic seizures are the major presentations of LGI1 antibody-mediated autoimmune diseases. The main feature of CASPR2 antibody disorders is hyperexcitability of the peripheral nervous system. MoS may exhibit any mix of these symptoms, contingent on the existence of antibodies against one or both of CASPR2 and LGI [33]. CASPR2, a transmembrane cell adhesion protein belonging to the neurexin superfamily, was initially reported in 1999. Its purpose is to control the recruitment of Kv1.1 and Kv1.2 VGKC subunits in the juxtaparanodal region of myelinated axons, which is crucial for appropriate electrical function.[34] Recently, an animal model showed that CASPR2 antibodies can also change the way that CASPR2 functions in the hippocampi. This results in fewer inhibitory neurons in the hippocampus and raises the possibility that antibody activity in the brain parenchyma could be a factor in the hyperexcitability of the central and peripheral nervous systems.[35] In terms of insomnia, MoS denotes functional disruptions in the thalamolimbic circuits that govern the autonomic nervous system and the sleep-wake cycle. In order to differentiate MoS from the deadly familial insomnia prion disease, which is typified by selectively severe atrophy of the thalamic mediodorsal and anteroventral nuclei with disconnection of the limbic cortical areas and subcortical regions, thalamic degeneration may be reversible in MoS.[36]

Clinical manifestation

A 47-year-old female living in Iran through a psychiatric clinic seeking to have her eyelid twitching stopped a common case called eyelid myokymia. She had combined TPM (topiramate) treatment in her routine for more than a year to be able to control binge eating and the resulting weight gain. At the beginning, twitching was well-endurable,

since it was not serious but during the episodes of stress or fatigue attacks. Nevertheless, the pain continues to intensify from time to time and became immune to the relief given by the past resting methods. Although she had been taught by investigating online and about anodyne nature of her illness, she kept on increasing her anxiety due to worsening symptoms. On review, the healthcare professionals did not notice any remarkable differences except for stable well-controlled Hypertension treated with Losartan. Having been asked to continue with her medications and also to take lot of rest, she came back after one month but this time around she had the twitching of the upper eyelid and occasionally the eyebrow on the same side although the twitching was more severe. Due to them physical deterioration, her self-image and social interactions suffered significantly to such a point where the medical team began to doubt TPM-related myokymia and advised to discontinue the medication. Initially unwilling as she lost a significant amount of weight, she reluctantly got support and medication. Surprised as I was, the course of my symptoms took a turn for the better, and completely healed in two weeks after I stopped the pills. Yet, the discontinuation of TPM resulted in her appetite intensifying and a weight gain afterwards, provoking severe emotional problems, and she entered a new depression. Accordingly, she then restarted with TPM and was shocked to find her eyelids were back on their myokymia within two weeks [37,38,39,40].

Diagnosis

Peripheral hyperexcitability is marked by severe cramps, myokymia, and neuromyotonia . Nerve condition studies (NCS) and electromyography (EMG) examination revealed a dominating neurogenic pattern with myokymia.[41] Confusion can readily develop when it is realized that clinical myokymia might exist even in the absence of myokymic discharges on EMG. Instead, high-frequency fasciculation potentials or neuromyotonic discharges can be observed, which mirror this clinical condition. Myokymic discharges, on the other hand, can be observed in the absence of clinical myokymia. In this context, the term “continuous motor unit activity” has been used to encompass the EMG results seen in stiff-person syndrome. However, this word lacks diagnostic specificity and should be avoided.

Fig.1: Pathophysiological features of fasciculation potentials, myokymic discharges, and neuromyotonic discharges.

The sources of peripheral hyperexcitability events are represented along the lower motor neuron (proximal vs. distal) based on the underlying reason. The putative pathogenic changes in channel activity that cause peripheral hyperexcitability symptoms are depicted. *A recent cohort research (Bashford et al., 2020a) found that the maximum fasciculation frequency in ALS was 360/min although doublets occur infrequently at intervals of 5-100 m/s, fasciculation potentials are mostly single. ALS, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; CASPR2, contactin2 associated protein 2; EC, extracellular; IC, intracellular; LGI1, leucine-rich glioma-inactivated 1; Nav, voltage-gated sodium channel; Na-K ATPase, sodium-potassium adenosine triphosphate-dependent pump; PNH, peripheral nerve hyperexcitability; VGKC, voltage-gated potassium channel complex.[42] Eyelid myokymia, in which patients notice spasms of the orbicularis oculi muscle, can cause a visual shift. This is generated by the eyelid pressing against the globe as the muscle fiber contract, thus it is not real oscillopsia or double vision. Clinical examination will reveal fine high-frequency fasciculations of the orbicularis oculi muscle that affect either the upper or lower eyelid.[43] Isaacs' syndrome is a rare acquired channel disease causing peripheral nerve hyperexcitability. It triggers autoantibodies to target presynaptic voltage-gated potassium channels, causing neurotransmitter release and muscle hyperexcitability. Symptoms include myokymia, neuro myotonia, muscle spasm, and stiffness, with clinical presentation.[44] Myokymia, a persistent interictal feature, is associated with KCNA1 but is also found in other EAs like EA3 and PxMD-UBR4. Persistent cerebellar dysfunction may occur in some patients, and non-neurological presentations include hypomagnesaemia.[45] The superior oblique muscle has 3 modes of action: incyclotorsion, depression, and abduction. Depending on the position of the eye, the role of these actions will vary (Fig. 2). In primary gaze, the superior oblique functions are primarily incyclotorsion and depression. With the eye in adduction, the muscle acts as a depressor, whereas in abduction, its function is incyclotorsion. Although the superior oblique also has abduction activity in primary gaze, its abduction function is most apparent with superior oblique overaction, often seen in patients with an A-pattern strabismus. At the insertion of the superior oblique on the globe, the anterior fibers impart a primarily incyclotorsional force, whereas the posterior fibers impart depressing and abducting forces.

Figure.2: action of the superior oblique muscle is shown in primary gaze (A), adduction (B), and abduction (C)

Figure.3: Quasi coronal MRI illustrates the appearance of the superior oblique (SO) in primary gaze and its increase in cross section size from elevation to depression. IR, inferior rectus, MR, medial rectus, SR, superior rectus[46].

Treatment

It is recommended that patients with isolated eyelid myokymia get conservative therapy. Effective management of eyelid myokymia involves rest, reduction, or removal of risk factors, such as alcohol consumption, smoking, and caffeine intake. If myokymia persists for more than three months, additional therapies could be required. Injections of botulinum toxin are a first-line treatment with a high success rate.[47] In the US, botulinum toxin has proven to be an effective treatment for chronic eyelid myokymia.[48] For chronic eyelid myokymia, a number of possible therapies have been suggested, including calcium, folic acid, phosphorus, potassium, and other vitamins;[48] Botulinum toxin injection: under myographic control, it is possible to inject the superior oblique muscle with botulinum toxin. However, it is difficult to do this without affecting the adjacent muscles and causing a superior oblique weakness with resultant double vision.[49] Five to twenty units of botulinum toxin are used, depending on the severity of the fasciculations. Other therapies, including tonic water, calcium, folic acid, phosphorus, potassium, and multivitamins, have been proposed for chronic eyelid myokymia. Nevertheless, there isn't any impartial proof in favor of these therapies.[50] If at all, an orbicularis myectomy is not recommended. One such remedy that has been anecdotally reported to be helpful for people with recurrent eyelid twitching is tonic water.[51] The hypothesized therapeutic mechanism of tonic water stems from one of its flavoring ingredients, quinine, an antimalarial that has demonstrated utility in the treatment of nocturnal leg cramps. Quinine is believed to exert this effect through the non-competitive inhibition of acetylcholine receptors at the neuromuscular junction.[51] For SOM, there is currently no approved treatment that works. The majority of SOM patients see the ophthalmologist due to visual problems. The inconsistent symptoms and remission intervals complicate the process of making a conclusive treatment evaluation. Moreover, fewer than 200 examples of the illness have been documented, making it unusual. The rare disorder known as superior oblique myokymia (SOM), whose genesis is unknown, causes oscillopsia and diplopia episodes. For SOM, there is no set course of treatment. Pharmacologic therapy aims to reduce the frequency of pathologic bursts of firing of the trochlear nerve; however, the mechanism of action (MOA) of these medications in relation to SOM is not yet entirely understood, but it is thought to be just an extension of their ordinary MOA.⁹ The original/prototypical medicine used for SOM was carbamazepine[52,53,54,55,56,57,58,] although it has major possible side effects such as leukopenia, acute renal failure, thrombosis, and arrhythmias.[52, 53,] Over the last 30 years, other oral drugs have been compared, explored, and investigated. Anecdotal evidence suggests that tonic water can help patients with recurrent eyelid twitching. Tonic water contains quinine, an antimalarial that has been shown to relieve nocturnal leg cramps, which is thought to be its therapeutic mechanism. Quinine is thought to produce this effect by non-competitively inhibiting acetylcholine receptors at the neuromuscular junction [59]. According to US Food and Drug Administration guidelines, quinine in food and beverage items may be present in as little as 83 parts per million. For example, a one-liter bottle of tonic water may contain up to 83 mg of quinine. Notably, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has advised against using quinine off-label for muscle cramps because of the possibility of serious negative consequences. Specifically, quinine overdose can cause cinchonism, a disorder that causes ataxia, tremors, tinnitus, and hearing loss [60]. Medical treatments for SOM that have been published include beta-blockers, phenytoin, carbamazepine, oxcarbazepine, gabapentin, and injections of botulinum toxin [61]. Nevertheless, SOM is a particularly challenging disorder to examine due to its low prevalence,

unclear etiology, and varied time course, and there are presently no proven treatments. We report a case of SOM that was effectively treated with Cinnabidinol oil. SOM is a difficult disorder to cure, and each patient responds differently to therapy. This case adds to the body of research on the potential use of Cannabidiol in neurological disorders and provides another treatment drug for SOM trials.

Surgery: When patients experience a return of uncontrollable symptoms or do not respond to medication therapies, surgery may be considered.[62]

Conclusion

The disorders where the eyelid and eye myokymia is not having any control over diagnosis and remedy are diagnose and treatment as the cause and the show are vary and wide ranged. Though it is a feature of life for all of us, it is yet fast enough to be overloaded with new information that it might take away from you in just a several minutes. It can as well indicate an occult condition, like all the ailments of the immune system such as deficient drugs like the topiramate whose side effects can be associated with it. Understanding neurotransmitters deeply such as alpha GABA and BK channels since they play a role in myokymia pathophysiology is the most critical aspect of developing the treatment.

It is the conservative approach and is comprised of medication therapy, bed rest and minimize the number of water activities. The actions serve the goals of arresting progression of the state. Hence, even though indirect effect of muscle overuse is not authority of botulinum toxin, it has been demonstrated that it can minimise muscle contractions. Cases like the ones that are undergoing trials to test drugs like carbamazepine and CBD oils are pending, but more research is needed before their effectiveness can be determined.

Surgery is recommended to be seen as a last resort in case of the unsuccess of standard therapies or when a person is diagnosed with a more severe kind of gender dysphoria. In the face of the risks of operation, the decision must be taken with deep resignation after counting on the gains and the losses involved.

To begin with, the therapy that works to treat myokymia is provided by specialized doctors from a neurology clinic that is supposed to work together with an ophthalmologist as well the other healthcare providers. Biographics deliver the background of the disease and the current methods of treatment these being the best ways to advantage patients concerning the disease.

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